

Case study 3:

Economic effects of adapting critical infrastructure in the Mannheim metropolitan area

Lessons learned

Work Package 3 – Deliverable 3.4

Delivery date: 31/03/2022

Dissemination Level: TBD

Authors: Fraunhofer IAIS: Erich Rome, Daniel Lücknerath, Katharina Milde

Lead beneficiary: NRI

Project full title: Unpacking climate impact chains - a new generation of climate change risk assessments

Project acronym: UNCHAIN

Grant Agreement number: 776608

Project start date: 1st September 2019

Funding scheme: H2020-SC5-2016-2017

Duration: 42 months

Title Lesson learned	Date 08/06/22
Project title Unpacking climate impact chains. A new generation of action- and user-oriented climate change risk assessments (UNCHAIN)	Number of pages 46
Lead authors Erich Rome, Daniel Lückerath, Katharina Milde	Project leader Carlo Aall

Contributors

–

Short summary

UNCHAIN deliverable D3.4 is a collection of twelve reports describing the lessons learned in the twelve UNCHAIN case studies. This report presents the findings of Case Study 3, titled “Economic effects of adapting critical infrastructure in the Mannheim metropolitan area”. It describes how the Vulnerability Sourcebook method for co-producing climate Impact Chains was applied in the case study, characterizes the results, and details the achieved innovations of the Impact Chain method. Case Study 3 shows how to combine different levels of scale, by starting with relevant parts of existing national Impact Chains, building regional Impact Chains based on these parts, and pinpointing risk factors from the regional Impact Chains to corporate units, processes, and activities (the corporate Value Chain). Regarding economic effects, the study assessed the impact of more frequent periods of low water of the Rhine River on costs of inland waterway transport of large volume goods for energy production.

Acknowledgements

Some parts of the English language text have been translated with www.DeepL.com/Translator (free version) from German text. The authors quality checked the automatic translation and made necessary corrections.

Table of contents

Table of contents.....	3
List of Figures.....	5
Introduction.....	6
1. Case brief description	6
2. Selected Impact Chain.....	8
3. Innovation areas and research questions addressed.....	9
I. Methodological approach to case study and related Impact Chain	10
1. Prepare Risk Assessment (Scoping).....	11
2. Developing Impact Chains.....	12
2.1 Developing Impact Chains	12
2.2 Eliciting Corporate Value Chains and pinpointing risk factors therein	14
3. Identifying and selecting indicators	19
4. Data acquisition and management	21
5. Normalizing indicators	22
6. Weighting.....	22
7. Aggregating indicators and components	23
II. Results (module 8: presenting RA outcomes).....	24
Risk Matrix as Excel Tool for Exploring Impacts of Low Water Scenarios.....	25
Visualization of Impact Chains.....	27
Additional information (“narratives” and other things)	29
III. Key lessons learned per innovation area.....	31
Research innovation relating to Impact Chain method.....	31
Research innovation relating to uncertainties	35
Research innovation relating to co-production of knowledge	35
Research innovation relating to societal change and socio-economic consequences	36
Research innovation relating to transborder climate change risks	37
Mapping of climate Impact Chains to Value Chains, logistics as connecting element	37
Adaptation of the visualization of the Impact Chain	37
Appendix 1: References.....	39
Appendix 2: Figures and Diagrams	43
National German Impact Chain, excerpt for low water IC.....	43

Complete, final, validated Impact Chain for low water risk.....	44
From national Impact Chains to impacts cascading along supply chains	45
Appendix 3: List of Acronyms	46

List of Figures

Figure 1: Modules of the Vulnerability Sourcebook [1] method for assessing risk related to effects of climate change.10

Figure 2: Value Chain of a company (after Porter [35]); light yellow, upper half: primary company activities; dark yellow, lower half: supporting company activities; orange, leading chevron shape: company margin.....14

Figure 3: Procedures for the elicitation of a Value Chain, for risk localization therein, for risk quantification and validation, as well as for the planning of adaptation measures.....15

Figure 4: Scheme of the corporate Value Chain. For each group of units, activities, and processes, a group of associated risk factors is determined.....17

Figure 5: Scheme of the corporate Value Chain enriched with risk factors (green: capacities; pink: sensitivities). The full enriched Value Chain created in Case Study 3 is confidential.18

Figure 6: Scheme of a Risk Matrix as proposed by German BBK [3]. Risk is represented as a function of Impact and Likelihood (sometimes Probability is used instead). In this example, both are subdivided into five discrete categories. Risk is subdivided into four categories which determine the urgency of required action. Typically, the assignment of Risk categories to combinations of Impact and Likelihood is based on political or management decisions. The number of categories may be adapted to the needs of the analysis at hand. Risk matrices are also mentioned in the standard ISO/IEC 31010 (2009) “Risk management – Risk assessment techniques” as ‘consequence criteria tables.’24

Figure 7: Risk matrix for transport surcharges per low water days in water level interval, i.e., likelihood based on frequency, and annual surcharges (impact). The colored matrix cells indicate the magnitude of the surcharge total per water level interval for each of the four years (2017, 2018, historic average, and a fictive scenario).....27

Figure 8: Excerpt of the German national Impact Chains, starting point for developing the low water IC in Case Study 3. After:
https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/380/dokumente/klimawirkungskette_n_umweltbundesamt_2016.pdf 43

Figure 9: Final, complete, validated Impact Chain for the risk of impacts of more frequent periods of drought and summer low water of the Rhine River on infrastructure and logistics in the Mannheim region (in German).44

Figure 10: Suggested use of Impact Chains at different levels of scale. Step 0: extract relevant parts from national ICs; step 1: create a regional case IC; step 2: map risk factors to the corporate Value Chain; step 3 (not applied): potential cascading of risk along a supply chain: leverage point for managing risk jointly with suppliers and customers45

Introduction

UNCHAIN deliverable D3.4 is a collection of twelve reports describing the lessons learned in the twelve UNCHAIN case studies. This report presents the findings of Case Study 3, titled “Economic effects of adapting critical infrastructure in the Mannheim metropolitan area”. The report follows a standard structure as agreed in the UNCHAIN project consortium.

In Case Study 3, the Fraunhofer team investigated environmental and economic effects of repeated long periods of heat, drought and of low water of the river Rhine, Europe’s most important inland waterway. The study area was the heavily industrialised metropolitan area of Mannheim. The study aimed at assessing the risk, the potential damages, the potential cost of damages and possible adaptation measures to infrastructure and industry (power generation, inland water transport, supply chains, etc.). Regarding the research and innovation aspects of the UNCHAIN project, the objective of the study was improving Impact Chain methods for assessing economic effects and creating a basis for assessing potential cascading effects. The selected case has trans-border aspects.

1. Case brief description

Case content

This case aims to further develop the Impact Chain method for analyzing risk originating from climate change. In this respect, it differs from an application-oriented risk assessment that solely aims at identifying risk factors and suitable adaptation options. For implementing the case, we conducted stakeholder dialogues and workshops for co-production of regional Impact Chains in a metropolitan area. Furthermore, we conducted a quantitative risk assessment that is focused on the economic effect of low waters of the Rhine River on costs of transporting freight via inland waterway. The case utilizes national Climate Impact Chains and maps risk factors to Value Chains of individual stakeholders, aiming at consistency across three distinct levels of scale (national – regional – company).

Research Innovations

Co-development of regional and individual (per stakeholder defined exposure) climate risk factors related to more frequent and extended periods of heat, drought, and low waters of the Rhine River; co-development of regional Impact Chains (ICs) that are consistent with the German national Climate Impact Chains; mapping risk factors (sensitivities, capacities, impacts) from regional ICs to Value Chains of single stakeholder organizations; assessing economic effects of low waters of the Rhine River.

Study areas

- Climate change-induced risks to and their socio-economic effects on infrastructure, with a focus on energy generation and inland waterway freight transport, and population in the metropolitan area of Mannheim, Germany
- Climate change-induced threats: more frequent and extended periods of heat, drought, and low waters of the Rhine River

Stakeholders involved

We included the following regional stakeholders in our assessment: municipal departments (Climate Office, Economic and Structural Development, Urban Development, Public Health Office, Professional Firefighters), state-owned Rhine-Neckar Port Authority, logistics company, energy producing company,

sanitary paper production company and researchers. Experts from the German Federal Institute of Hydrology contributed expertise and data.

Summary data collection

- Qualitative data has been gathered through stakeholder dialogues and workshops
- Quantitative data, such as socio-demographic and socio-economic data, has been partly
 - collected from various open government data portals and other freely and openly available sources,
 - provided by stakeholders, and
 - provided by a federal institute.

Results

Two validated Impact Chains, one IC became part of the heat action plan of the City of Mannheim; case documentation; mapping of individual risk factors to the Value Chain of an energy producer; Value Chain model; risk analysis; Excel tool for estimating additional waterway transportation costs based on characteristics of low water at the Rhine River.

Case study responsible

Fraunhofer IAIS, Sankt Augustin (Fraunhofer)

Context of the vulnerability assessment

For the last 70 years (1952-2021), droughts have only been a problem in Germany in some years and rarely affected the entire country. Before the year 2010, significant droughts occurred in 1959, 1960, 1964, 1973, 1976, and 2003 in the period considered. After 2010, droughts occurred more frequently. For three years in a row (2018-2020), practically the entire country was affected by drought (see German Drought Monitor at <https://www.ufz.de/index.php?de=47252>). The year 2018 also brought an extremely prolonged period of extreme low waters of the Rhine River, leading to significantly reduced freight transport volumes on Europe's most important inland waterway and to high economic losses for several major industries located along the Rhine.

Older regional studies of effects of climate change on ground water availability and low waters of inland waterways have been inconclusive in predicting future trends. However, more recent studies (from 2019 on, published in 2020 and 2021) predict reduced availability of groundwater and more frequent periods of low waters for rivers in some pathway scenarios with more certainty. The topic will remain subject of further scientific investigation.

Adaptation measures are already being taken, both in enterprises—including infrastructure operators—and in politics. In enterprises, adaptation measures are referring to, for example, business continuity management, health protection of workers, secured water supply, use of renewable energy, and improved and intelligent logistics. In politics, the German Federal Ministry of Transport and Digital Infrastructure has issued an eight-point "Action plan low water Rhine" [7] for securing the freight transport on the Rhine River. This complements other policies, like the German Adaptation Strategy [12], the Federal Program "Blue Belt Germany" [8] aimed at protecting the ecology of federal inland waterways, and international policies at EU level, as well as activities of international organizations overseeing the implementation of treaties regarding the Rhine River. A German specialty is the fact that the national government has included German national Climate Impact Chains [43],[45] in the German Adaptation Strategy [12], structured into twelve fields of action.

Objectives and expected outcomes

In the European Union, more than 72% of the population lives in cities and built-up areas (source: EUROSTAT), and the trend is rising. The BMZ¹[11] stated that cities generate up to 80% of the gross domestic product. Finally, cities also bundle much of the social and technical infrastructure for services of general interest, including critical infrastructure. The well-being of the population and the flourishing of the economy thus depend to a considerable extent on the functioning of urban infrastructure. On a European level, several new or updated policies ([17], [18], [19]) acknowledge this fact and require measures for making infrastructures and 'critical entities' more resilient to threats—including threats induced by Climate Change—and climate neutral. While such policies become increasingly mutually consistent, the included requirement of using synergies when implementing resilience-enhancing measures points at a fundamental limitation, namely the availability of funds for the implementation. Assessing the effectiveness and efficiency of proposed measures will become vital for raising the required funds. Measures to increase the resilience of infrastructure can be better assessed if the threats posed by climate change impacts and the effects of infrastructure failure are better understood, particularly their socio-economic dimension. Despite public awareness of infrastructure vulnerability to extreme weather events, only few economic assessments of future infrastructure developments under different climate scenarios, like recently [21], have been developed. Reasons for this may be several barriers, including lack of precise and comprehensive data; lack of methods to scale down from national to regional or local level; infrastructures alone form already a complex system of systems that is hard to analyze, and some analysis results may need to be kept confidential for security reasons; the economic dependencies form another complex system of systems.

The UNCHAIN Case Study 3 addresses likelihoods by working with the City of Mannheim and other regional stakeholders to assess the risk to industries, services, and logistics companies represented by potential infrastructure service reduction.

For taking the trans-sectoral and trans-national orientation of the project into account, the case study focused on the major metropolitan region of Mannheim, the companies and residents located there as well as relevant critical infrastructure, particularly energy production and freight transport via the Rhine River. A specific goal was to connect the risk analysis to the more general national climate Impact Chains on one hand, and to individual stakeholders' business continuity management on the other hand, spanning three levels of scale.

Involved researchers were Daniel Lückerrath, Katharina Milde, and Erich Rome (all Fraunhofer).

2. Selected Impact Chain

Some UNCHAIN case studies have produced more than one Impact Chain. In the case study report (i.e., this deliverable), only one such Impact Chain shall be reported in detail. For Case Study 3, we selected the Impact Chain titled "Risk of negative effects of extended periods of drought and low water of the river Rhine on logistics and infrastructure in the metropolitan area."

¹ German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development

3. Innovation areas and research questions addressed

Case Study 3 aimed at two innovation areas in UNCHAIN, namely “Impact Chain Model & Uncertainty” (ICM&U) and “Socio-economic Scenarios” (SES). Based on successful application experiences in previous projects, “Co-production of knowledge” (CPK) was the method of choice, therefore we also strived for innovation in this field. Lastly, the case study investigated impacts of Climate Change on freight transport and energy production, with the potential to contribute to the fourth innovation area “Trans-border climate change impacts” (TBCCI).

It should be noted that the case study evolved over a span of two years, resulting in some changes compared to the original idea (the focus on a seaport and inland harbours was shifted towards logistics and infrastructure in a metropolitan area located at the Rhine River). Also, the specific contents needed to be adapted to the local situation in the study area and the adaptation status and needs of the involved stakeholders. In UNCHAIN, 21 research questions were formulated to guide the overall research process in the project for improving the methodological IC approach. We were able to address most of those 12 Research Questions (RQs) that we had initially selected as candidate RQs for Case Study 3, but not all of them. The remaining, addressed RQs are listed below.

Innovation area “Impact Chain Model & Uncertainty”

- ICM&U-1. How to identify the relevant system elements and their interrelations when doing Impact Chain analysis?
- ICM&U-1.1. How to better support identification of system elements / include knowledge from all relevant impact fields?
- ICM&U-1.5. How to combine a multitude of (sector-specific) information and still present them in a clear and concise manner?
- ICM&U-4. How to address limitations in the availability of reliable data? (Heterogeneity, spatial/temporal resolution, the mismatch between resolution)

Innovation area “Co-production of knowledge”

- CPK-4. What are the benefits of adopting an integrated approach combining knowledge co-production and impact modelling?

Innovation area “Socio-economic scenarios”

- SES-1. How to include future vulnerability conditions based on socio-economic scenarios to better depict future critical conditions?
- SES-2. How to gain a better understanding of socioeconomic consequences involved in climate change adaptation?
- SES-3. How to combine the differences in scale between where statistical data is produced (within administrative borders at national, county, or municipal levels) and where the impacts of climate change manifest itself (mostly independent of administrative borders)?
- SES-5. How do we ensure that local/context-specific 'first experiences' with Impact Chain methodology and framework are fed back into the improvement of the framework?

Innovation area “Transborder climate change impacts”

- TBCCI-1. What are the most important transborder climate change risk in the involved countries/cases?
- TBCCI-3. Who (private/public actors, at various levels and within different sectors) are most accountable for managing different sub-categories of transborder climate change risks?

The next section is structured along the modules—or process steps—of the Vulnerability Sourcebook [1], the reference publication on the Impact Chain method for risk assessment. For each of the modules that we applied in Case Study 3, we report the module specific results related to the RQs. This will cover all but one of the RQs listed above. The second RQ in the innovation area CPK (CPK-2) relates to results of stakeholder feedback. Results from Case Study 3 regarding CPK-2 will be addressed in a deliverable of work package 4.

I. Methodological approach to case study and related Impact Chain

The presentation of the approach employed for Case Study 3 is structured along the modules—or process steps—of the Vulnerability Sourcebook (VSB, [1]). This serves two purposes: 1) to map the methodological improvements gained in Case Study 3 explicitly onto the process steps of the original method and 2) to facilitate linkages with the WP5 deliverable that presents the overarching evaluation of methodological innovation across all UNCHAIN case studies.

Figure 1: Modules of the Vulnerability Sourcebook [1] method for assessing risk related to effects of climate change.

1. Prepare Risk Assessment (Scoping)

RQ addressed

- ICM&U-1. How to identify the relevant system elements and their interrelations when doing Impact Chain analysis?
- ICM&U-1.1. How to better support identification of system elements / include knowledge from all relevant impact fields?

Process

Implementing the case study started with extending the regional stakeholder network, elaborating the initial case ideas, and collecting information on the regional situation (the context). These actions mutually influenced each other. New stakeholders required our familiarisation with their adaptation goals, existing resilience measures, and with sector and corporate information. Preferences regarding the planned assessment had to be included in the implementation plan. Nevertheless, the preparation process included the same steps as outlined in the Vulnerability Sourcebook [1].

For understanding the context of the risk assessment, the researchers collected and studied material on identified climate risks, impacts, and adaptation measures, including:

- National Impact Chains (of the German Federal Environmental Agency) [43], [45]
- German climate studies [10], [30], [46]
- National and local adaptation strategies, monitoring reports, action plans [7], [8], [9], [29], [46]
- Risk analyses, stress tests [2], [3], [10], [17], [25], [32], [41]
- Advanced methods [6], [27], [28], [36], [44]
- Case studies [31], [37], [38], [41]
- Annual reports of relevant national and international agencies and bodies (e.g., CCNR, German federal transport infrastructure plan) [46], [9]
- Reports and analyses on economic damages of the summer low water of the Rhine River [5], [17], [22], [39]
- Stakeholder (annual) business reports, stakeholder presentations
- Sector-related information [5], [6], [13], [15]

For identifying the stakeholder objectives and expected outcomes, we interviewed the stakeholder group. The City of Mannheim had a clear preference on the risk of extended heat waves but was also interested in the effect of prolonged and more frequent periods of low waters of the Rhine River. The other stakeholders were interested in both threats but did not have a specific need for risk assessment. Also, we learned that they had already implemented some adaptation measures related to low waters. Their interest was more focused on learning about the Impact Chain method and on learning how companies from other sectors implemented adaptation measures (best practices). The expected outcome, besides gaining new knowledge, were the co-produced Impact Chains.

For determining the scope of the vulnerability assessment, we agreed on the creation of at least one qualitative IC, which was partly influenced by the limited resources of all case study participants.

For preparing an implementation plan, we had to regard the pure online nature of the workshops, which required finding easy to use but suitable tools for co-production of ICs. The finally selected tool

was the *miro*² online whiteboard. Also, we employed the relevant parts of existing national German ICs as a basis for the IC templates. For preparing the agenda of the workshops, we created detailed moderation plans, defining roles of participants, tools, and methods to use, and outcomes of each agenda item. For each workshop, we also designed the preparatory and post-processing steps.

Outcomes

The outcomes of the scoping phase included minutes of the agreements with stakeholders, a large body of background literature, a concept for the implementation of the risk assessment, and an online whiteboard instance of the graphical template for the selected IC, partially filled with relevant parts of the national ICs.

2. Developing Impact Chains

In Case Study 3, we have extended VSB module M2 by an optional step consisting of connecting ICs to individual stakeholders' business continuity management in a subsequent analysis stage. The subsequent stage maps risk factors from the ICs onto elements—i.e., business units and processes—of a corporate Value Chain (VC). Therefore, we have split this section up and describe both the co-production of the IC and of the VC.

2.1 Developing Impact Chains

RQ addressed

- ICM&U-1. How to identify the relevant system elements and their interrelations when doing Impact Chain analysis?
- ICM&U-1.1. How to better support identification of system elements / include knowledge from all relevant impact fields?

Process

Within the course of Case Study 3, two Impact Chains were developed in co-creation with stakeholders from Mannheim. The process of creating the Impact Chains was further developed during the case study. The two Impact Chains differ in scope, content, and stakeholders that participated and lay the foundation for a further use and/or analysis on these different levels of scopes.

The first Impact Chain developed shows the **negative impacts of heat waves on the population** (especially on vulnerable groups) in Mannheim. Stakeholders involved in the creation were representatives of the Mannheim Climate Protection Department, Mannheim Professional Firefighters, Mannheim Public Health Department, Urban Development and Economic and Structural Development Departments. Prior to the Impact Chain workshop, Fraunhofer prepared an initial version of the Impact Chain based on the German national Impact Chains³ published by the German Environment Agency (UBA). The initial version of the Impact Chain was visualized in a *miro*-board Causal connections were not shown in correspondence to the Impact Chain layout from the Vulnerability Sourcebook [1] and steps to moderate and develop the Impact Chain were included. In the workshop, that was held online,

² *miro* is an online whiteboard tool for participative group work, well suited for co-production techniques like brainwriting.

³ https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/380/dokumente/klimawirkungsketten_umweltbundesamt_2016.pdf

the *miro*-board was further filled jointly with the stakeholders alongside the prepared questions and comments. In the workshop, first, the Impact Chain methodology was explained to the participants, then the individual participants explained the impacts of heat waves on the population that are relevant to their field of expertise or from their experience. Based on this exchange, the individual sections of the Impact Chain were further filled. The results of the workshop were subsequently analysed and restructured by Fraunhofer and supplemented with suggestions for causal relationships. To simplify the layout, individual areas of the Impact Chain were “broken up” and consequences, sensitivities and capacities were assigned to the different fields of impact. The documentation of the workshop and the outcomes was provided to the participants. Furthermore, the city of Mannheim used an adapted visualisation of the Impact Chain for their heat action plan.

The **second Impact Chain** developed in the case study—the one selected for this report—covers “**Impacts of more frequent periods of drought and summer low water of the Rhine on infrastructure and logistics in the Mannheim region**”. The Impact Chain was developed with local stakeholders from the city of Mannheim and corporations based in Mannheim: the Mannheim Climate Protection Department, the Mannheim Professional Firefighters, the state-owned Rhine-Neckar Port Authority, contargo GmbH, the Mannheim Large Powerplant, essity, the Federal Institute of Hydrology. In the Impact Chain workshop, a researcher from the Institut National des Sciences Appliquées de Strasbourg, an UNCHAIN research partner, was also involved.

Prior to working together with the experts and local stakeholders, Fraunhofer prepared an initial Impact Chain for the workshop. This version contained extracted information from different climate Impact Chains of the German Environment Agency (UBA) and was visualized—without causal connections—in a *miro*-board and corresponding to the Impact Chain layout from the Vulnerability Sourcebook [1]. In this version, Fraunhofer already clustered consequences, sensitivities and capacities based on the fields of action of the German Adaptation Strategy and added some questions and comments to guide the workshop (e.g., reference to further fields of action).

In a joint workshop (lasting approximately four hours) with the above-mentioned stakeholders from Mannheim and the UNCHAIN project, the initial Impact Chain was systematically expanded. First, the Impact Chain method was explained before individual participants explained the relevant impacts of dry periods and summer low water on their companies and specialist areas based on their experience. Based on this exchange, the individual sections of the Impact Chain were further filled-in during a moderated working session. The workshop concluded with collecting sensitivities and capacities. This approach encouraged the participants to discuss with each other their individual or sector perspectives on and approaches to risk and adaptation, leading to mutual awareness of which adaptation measures are necessary for whom or are already in use.

In a next step, Fraunhofer analysed the collected information and developed proposals for restructuring, simplification, and causal connections. This version was provided to the participants and their feedback was implemented. The final outcome, the validated Impact Chain, can be found in Figure 9.

Outcomes

The first co-produced Impact Chain presents the risk factors of negative impacts of heat waves on the population (especially on vulnerable groups) in Mannheim. The second co-produced Impact Chain presents the risk factors of negative impacts of extended periods of drought and low waters of the Rhine River on infrastructure, logistics and population in the metropolitan area of Mannheim.

2.2 Eliciting Corporate Value Chains and pinpointing risk factors therein

RQ addressed

- ICM&U-1. How to identify the relevant system elements and their interrelations when doing Impact Chain analysis?
- ICM&U-1.1. How to better support identification of system elements / include knowledge from all relevant impact fields?
- ICM&U-4. How to address limitations in the availability of reliable data? (Heterogeneity, spatial/temporal resolution, the mismatch between resolution)

Process

The concept of the Value Chain was developed by the American economist Michael E. Porter who introduced it in his 1985 book *“Competitive Advantage: Creating and Sustaining Superior Performance”* [34]. Porter’s concept of the Value Chain divides a company’s activities into primary and supporting activities. Value chain diagrams describe these company activities in graphical form (Figure 2). The division of a company’s activities into areas and interlocking processes that take place in these areas and across areas offers various opportunities for analysis and optimization.

Figure 2: Value Chain of a company (after Porter [35]); light yellow, upper half: primary company activities; dark yellow, lower half: supporting company activities; orange, leading chevron shape: company margin.

A fundamental prerequisite for being able to carry out such analyses at all is an in-depth understanding of the company’s activities. For developing an understanding of where the value creation takes places, Porter [35] (p. 98f, 104) suggests asking specific guiding question, such as: Why is the company successful? Why is it more profitable than its competitors? What exactly does the company do very well? Answers to these questions may give rise to follow-up questions, and repeatedly so. Ideally, the result is a chain of causality that includes all or most of the factors that determine the value creation. To

practically answer such fundamental questions and to create Value Chains, one must acquire knowledge from company experts on how their company operates. This can be done by means of interviews or by facilitated participative workshops with company experts.

We designed the assessment of the climate change risk for Value Chains of a company as a multi-step process with up to four steps within module 2 of the VSB. This procedure requires an Impact Chain as input, i.e., it is subsequent to the procedure described in section 2.2. The Impact Chain could be a regional Impact Chain or a corporate Impact Chain. In both cases, the risk elements of the Impact Chain shall be pinpointed in the Value Chain elements.

The individual steps of the proposed procedure for eliciting a corporate Value Chain are adapted to the individual needs and the existing information and data situation of the company to achieve a result that is useful for the users. Whenever possible, the process can (and should) build on existing results and information. In the final fifth step, the risk analysis is validated, and exemplary adaptation measures are derived. Figure 3 provides an overview of the individual steps of the procedure.

The development of all results takes place in cooperation between Fraunhofer and representatives of the company by means of discussions, information exchange via e-mail, and through workshops. In total, a maximum of four half-day workshops can be expected, in addition to a preliminary discussion of up to 90 minutes duration and possible further short periods of time for validation of the results. The participants from the company are ideally one or two main contact persons and, if necessary, experts on specific company areas (depending on the planned scope of the in-depth risk analysis). The steps of the process are briefly explained below.

Figure 3: Procedures for the elicitation of a Value Chain, for risk localization therein, for risk quantification and validation, as well as for the planning of adaptation measures

Step 0: Determination of the objective and the available (personnel) resources.

Together with the users, the goal of the risk analysis is specified in more detail: How detailed should the risk analysis be? Which company departments or persons should be involved? What information is available (organizational charts, process manuals, annual business reports, etc.)? What do confidentiality agreements look like? When should the next step be taken? The agreements are recorded in a results protocol.

Step 1: Elicitation of a company's Value Chain.

If a documentation of a corporate Value Chain does not exist, it needs to be elicited. In Case Study 3, researchers and stakeholders have performed this elicitation jointly. The level of detail can vary depending on the objectives and available time/personnel resources. At a minimum, the different company divisions involved in the value creation (e.g., purchasing/procurement, sales, production, etc.) and their activities and core processes should be included. Preliminary information, e.g., organizational charts or descriptions of the structural and process organization, can be used for preparation. Areas of the Value Chain that are particularly interesting and/or affected by climate change can then be broken down in more detail, if necessary. The intermediate result of this step is the Value Chain of the company in diagram form. Afterwards, the terminology can be harmonized, and the presentation can be made more precise, which is then validated by the participants before the next step.

A catalog of questions on the following topics is prepared for the elicitation of the corporate Value Chain:

- Organization, products, and customers of the company
- Value chains of the company (if already elicited)
- Core processes and value creation processes of the company
- Check for completeness

The elicitation approach should lead from the organization to individual processes, roughly in the following order:

- 1) Building understanding of the business and the organization.
- 2) Identification of organizational units relevant for value creation and their sequence (per product)
- 3) Identification of process steps within organizational units and their sequence (per product)
- 4) Understanding of the company's resilience mechanisms (e.g., business continuity management, IT security)
- 5) Other interrelationships and relevant external business factors (e.g., market and market mechanisms)
- 6) Categorization according to core processes, support processes and management processes

Intended outcomes of the elicitation include:

- List / mapping of organizational units relevant for value creation and their interrelationships (per product)
- List / mapping of process steps within individual organizational units (per product)
- External factors relevant for the business
- Visualization of the Value Chain (see Figure 4)
- Subdivision into core processes, support processes, management processes

Figure 4: Scheme of the corporate Value Chain. The full Value Chain created in Case Study 3 is confidential. For each group of units, activities, and processes, a group of associated risk factors is designated.

Step 2: Locating the climatic risk factors in the Value Chain.

Based on the post-processed Value Chain and the pre-defined risk to be investigated, Fraunhofer and the stakeholders jointly record the potential climate change-related impacts on individual areas and process steps of the Value Chain (e.g., delivery delays or failures, increased production costs, necessary changes in regular transport modes) as well as the relevant associated risk factors. The intermediate result of this step is the Value Chain with the relevant risk elements from the climate Impact Chain assigned to the business units, activities, and process steps (see Figure 5). If a climate Impact Chain (IC) already exists, its risk elements (hazards, sensitivities, capacities, impacts) can be assigned to the Value Chain and, if necessary, further specified.

In Case Study 3, the joint researcher and stakeholder team transferred relevant risk factor from the second regional IC (“drought and low water risk”) to appropriate elements in the Value Chain. Subsequently, the stakeholders named additional company-specific risk factors that were also pinpointed to elements of the Value Chain. Figure 5 shows the graphical scheme of the enriched Value Chain.

As before, harmonization and clarifications that still need to be validated can be made subsequently.

Figure 5: Scheme of the corporate Value Chain enriched with risk factors (green: capacities; pink: sensitivities). Each element of the Value Chain may have any number of assigned capacities and sensitivities. The full enriched Value Chain created in Case Study 3 is confidential.

Step 3: Consolidation and selection of indicators, determination of data sources, assessing risk quantitatively. In this step, the risk is assessed and visualized along the Value Chain. If sufficient data is available, a quantitative risk assessment can be made; otherwise, a semi-quantitative risk assessment can be made using expert estimates. Even with good availability of company data, it is possible that indicator data cannot be provided in nominal form due to confidentiality. In such cases, (partial) anonymization techniques can be applied, such as conversion to percentage values or reporting additional costs instead of total costs. This step is methodically identical to module 3 of the Vulnerability Sourcebook (see section 3), but uses the risk-enhanced Value Chain as input instead of the Impact Chain.

In Case Study 3, the joint team proposed indicators for each linkage of risk element / process step / element of the Value Chain. The result is a table containing potential indicators per combination of risk area, element of the Value Chain (business unit), process step in that element, and risk factor (like impact, capacity, sensitivity). For each potential indicator, its dimension and data availability are entered. Table 1 shows an excerpt of the generated table.

The joint team selected one indicator for further quantitative analysis, namely “Additional costs for inland water freight transport during low water periods”. The details of the quantitative analysis are covered in Section 4 Data acquisition and management.

Step 4: Identification of potential adaptation measures and their impacts. Based on the calculated risk, a check is made for the most severely affected areas and process steps in the Value Chain to determine whether and, if so, which adaptation measures are required. To do this, it is first necessary to identify the resilience mechanisms already in place, which are components of business continuity management, or which result from external market mechanisms. Then, the effects of the adaptation measures are determined, both direct effects on the Value Chain (e.g., changes in process flow) and indirect effects (e.g., increased production costs).

In Case Study 3, this final step 4 was omitted due to time and resource constraints.

Outcomes

Value chain of an energy producer in which relevant risk factors from the IC are pinpointed to business units and processes and complemented with individual risk factors.

3. Identifying and selecting indicators

RQ addressed

- ICM&U-1. How to identify the relevant system elements and their interrelations when doing Impact Chain analysis?
- ICM&U-1.1. How to better support identification of system elements / include knowledge from all relevant impact fields?
- ICM&U-4. How to address limitations in the availability of reliable data? (Heterogeneity, spatial/temporal resolution, the mismatch between resolution)
- SES-1. How to include future vulnerability conditions based on socio-economic scenarios to better depict future critical conditions?
- SES-2. How to gain a better understanding of socioeconomic consequences involved in climate change adaptation?
- SES-3. How to combine the differences in scale between where statistical data is produced (within administrative borders at national, county, or municipal levels) and where the impacts of climate change manifest itself (mostly independent of administrative borders)?

Process

Indicators were only identified for the combined, risk-enhanced Impact & Value Chain developed with the Mannheim Large Powerplant. Based on the risk-enhanced Impact & Value Chain, Fraunhofer developed initial suggestions for qualitative indicators (for potential use in a narrative) and (semi-)quantitative indicators (for which data might be available or which could be estimated using expert judgments). These indicators were categorized into

- the different risk factors (hazard, exposure, impact, sensitivity, capacity),
- the different business areas found in the Value Chain (inbound logistics, provision, production, maintenance, outbound logistics, etc.), and
- the different process steps within the Value Chain – if possible.

For each of these indicators, Fraunhofer also provided initial suggestions for the dimensions in which they might be measured (e.g., tons of coal, duration of disruptions in hours) and results of a first survey of publicly available data. This resulted in a list of some 55 indicators.

This indicator list was reviewed by the stakeholders from the Mannheim Large Powerplant and then discussed between Fraunhofer and the stakeholders in two conference calls. During these calls, the following questions were answered for each indicator:

- Is the indicator measurable by the stakeholders?
- Is data available to calculate the indicator?
- Is there already another indicator that measures the same effect (i.e., is the indicator redundant)?
- Would it be possible to estimate the indicator using expert judgements?
- Are other – qualitative – information sources available for the indicator?

This resulted in a first reduction of the number of indicators to some 33. Of these 33 indicators, 26 were judged to be potentially (semi-)quantifiable, while the rest was judged to be useful for a qualitative evaluation.

Not for all potentially quantifiable indicators, it was immediately clear whether sufficient data would be available (see also next section/step). Therefore, the remaining indicators underwent another review process by GKM and Fraunhofer. As a result, it was decided to focus the quantitative analysis on transport costs due to prolonged periods of low tide, which reduced the number of quantifiable indicators to 5.

Outcomes

List of indicators, categorized according to related risk component, business unit, and process step with additional information on measurement dimension and data availability (see Table 1).

Indicators for which data are available or estimates could be made						
	Element of the Value Chain	Process step	Impact	Potential Indicator(s)	Dimension	Data availability
Procurement risk	Transport / Input	Transport (to ARA sea-ports)	Higher costs	Additional costs for inland water freight transport during low water periods	€	Derivable from low water surcharge (KWZ), gauge level history and transport quantities history
Procurement risk	Transport / Input	Inland transport	Reduction of payload per barge	Freight quantities	Quantity per barge	Correlates with number of barges
Procurement risk	Transport / Input	Inland transport	Increased demand for barges	Number of barges	–	Derivable from number of barges / gauge

						level, gauge level history and transport history
--	--	--	--	--	--	--

Table 1: Excerpt of the table of proposed indicators per element of the Value Chain, process step, and risk factor (here: impact).

4. Data acquisition and management

RQ addressed

- ICM&U-4. How to address limitations in the availability of reliable data? (Heterogeneity, spatial/temporal resolution, the mismatch between resolution)
- SES-1. How to include future vulnerability conditions based on socio-economic scenarios to better depict future critical conditions?
- SES-2. How to gain a better understanding of socioeconomic consequences involved in climate change adaptation?
- SES-3. How to combine the differences in scale between where statistical data is produced (within administrative borders at national, county, or municipal levels) and where the impacts of climate change manifest itself (mostly independent of administrative borders)?

Process

In parallel to the indicator definition / selection, Fraunhofer started to acquire and analyse available public hazard data. Specifically, Fraunhofer acquired historic records for the gauging stations Kaub and Mannheim in the River Rhine from the Federal Institute of Hydrology. The station Mannheim was chosen due to its vicinity to the Mannheim Large Powerplant, while the station Kaub was chosen as it is the critical bottleneck for transport logistics of the Rhine River. These datasets included daily mean gauging levels for the period 1900 to 2020, as well as 15-minute interval gauging levels for the period 2005 to 2020. Analysing the 15-minute intervals for station Kaub to calculate the length and number of consecutive intervals in which the gauging level fell within a specific surcharge interval (see next paragraph) showed that for the intended analysis of economic costs the 15-minute interval data was too detailed and the daily mean values would be sufficient. This is the case, because the transportation time from the ARA⁴ harbours to the Mannheim harbor is so long, that only very extensive, consecutive intervals of low water become relevant for the transportation surcharge. Therefore, these intervals can also be identified using the daily mean gauging levels, instead of the 15-minute interval dataset.

From the Mannheim Large Powerplant, Fraunhofer received two historical datasets: 1) the monthly amount of coal—in t—transported for the years 2017 and 2018; and 2) the transport surcharge—in €—that needs to be paid per t of coal for different gauging levels at station Kaub. In addition to these datasets, Fraunhofer analysed several different studies and reports to acquire additional knowledge

⁴ ARA: Amsterdam, Rotterdam, Antwerp (seaports)

and information on transport dynamics and interdependencies of coal-based power generation (see section 1).

Outcomes

Collection of reports / studies with relevance to the case study, a Python script to calculate the length and number of consecutive low water intervals based on the 15-minute interval data, an Excel file to calculate the probability of days where the daily mean gauging level at station Kaub lies within the transportation cost intervals as provided by the Mannheim Powerplant.

5. Normalizing indicators

RQ addressed

- ICM&U-4. How to address limitations in the availability of reliable data? (Heterogeneity, spatial/temporal resolution, the mismatch between resolution)
- SES-3. How to combine the differences in scale between where statistical data is produced (within administrative borders at national, county, or municipal levels) and where the impacts of climate change manifest itself (mostly independent of administrative borders)?

Process

In the Vulnerability Sourcebook, the procedure of normalization is recommended as a pre-processing step before combining indicators with different dimensions or value ranges for the purpose of aggregation. Since in Case Study 3 we studied only one indicator, the VSB modules M5–M7 did not apply. However, the indicator that we studied, the transport surcharge for low water freight transport on the Rhine River, required a different form of normalization. The surcharge is directly depended on a reference gauge level at station Kaub and may vary daily. Also, the historic gauge level values showed that the water levels in any two years typically vary in period, amount, and dates. This makes it hard to make predictions and to compare scenarios. Therefore, we created a reference scenario based on the 120 years average (1900–2020) of gauge level values for use with an *Excel* tool for estimating and comparing water transport surcharges for different low water scenarios, described in sections 7 and II.

We created the reference scenario by calculating the number of days per year in which the daily mean gauging level at station Kaub falls within specific surcharge intervals as provided by the Mannheim Large Powerplant. Based on these values, we calculated the 120-year average, which is used to calculate the expected surcharge for an ‘average year’ against which historical or fictive scenarios can be compared.

Outcomes

Evaluated set of historic data on water levels of the Rhine River at the gauging station Kaub for a 120-year period (1900–2020); calculated number of days per year where water levels fall within intervals that are relevant for transport surcharges; average number of such days for the period; data on total annual and average daily volume of fuel transported by cargo ship on the Rhine River (for reference years 2017 and 2018); transport surcharges per t (for the relation Rotterdam seaport to Mannheim) in relevant water level intervals; reference scenario based on the calculated 120 year average.

6. Weighting

Weighting was not addressed in Case Study 3.

7. Aggregating indicators and components

RQ addressed

- ICM&U-4. How to address limitations in the availability of reliable data? (Heterogeneity, spatial/temporal resolution, the mismatch between resolution)
- SES-1. How to include future vulnerability conditions based on socio-economic scenarios to better depict future critical conditions?
- SES-2. How to gain a better understanding of socioeconomic consequences involved in climate change adaptation?

As stated previously, the ‘usual’ approach to indicator aggregation as advocated in the VSB could not be used for Case Study 3. On the one hand, because no quantifiable vulnerability and exposure indicators were available, but only a hazard indicator (the gauging levels) and an impact indicator (transportation surcharge). On the other hand, using the ‘usual’ aggregation method from the VSB was also not desired, because it ignores the (intermediate) impacts – as they are dependent on hazards and vulnerabilities – and only results in a single risk score and no economic impact estimate.

Therefore, Fraunhofer chose to employ the risk matrix approach for risk calculation as employed by the German Federal Office for Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance (BBK) [3]. Using this method had the additional advantage of familiarity, since the Mannheim Large Powerplant also uses a risk matrix approach for other operational aspects. In this approach, the estimated transportation costs under a given scenario are categorized in six different impact levels, while the probability of a certain number of days per year where the gauging level at station Kaub falls within a specific surcharge interval is categorized in five different likelihood levels. The combination of impact and likelihood then gives the risk classification (see Figure 6).

Figure 6: Scheme of a Risk Matrix as proposed by German BBK [3]. Risk is represented as a function of Impact and Likelihood (sometimes Probability is used instead). In this example, both are subdivided into five discrete categories. Risk is subdivided into four categories which determine the urgency of required action. Typically, the assignment of Risk categories to combinations of Impact and Likelihood is based on political or management decisions. The number of categories may be adapted to the needs of the analysis at hand. Risk matrices are also mentioned in the standard ISO/IEC 31010 (2009) “Risk management – Risk assessment techniques” as ‘consequence criteria tables.’

For use in Case Study 3, we adopted this scheme for the classification of the impact of days with low water levels on transport surcharges for shipping fuel from Rotterdam to Mannheim via cargo ship on the Rhine River.

Outcomes

Excel tool for comparing low water scenarios and the resulting transport surcharge for freight transport on the Rhine River

II. Results (module 8: presenting RA outcomes)

RQ addressed

- ICM&U-1. How to identify the relevant system elements and their interrelations when doing Impact Chain analysis?
- ICM&U-1.1. How to better support identification of system elements / include knowledge from all relevant impact fields?
- CPK-2. How were results from the climate risk assessment perceived by stakeholders and scientific knowledge providers?
- CPK-4. What are the benefits of adopting an integrated approach combining knowledge co-production and impact modelling?
- SES-1. How to include future vulnerability conditions based on socio-economic scenarios to better depict future critical conditions?
- SES-2. How to gain a better understanding of socioeconomic consequences involved in climate change adaptation?
- TBCCI-1. What are the most important transborder climate change risk in the involved countries/cases?
- TBCCI-3. Who (private/public actors, at various levels and within different sectors) are most accountable for managing different sub-categories of transborder climate change risks?

Process

Risk Matrix as Excel Tool for Exploring Impacts of Low Water Scenarios

As mentioned in the previous sections, Fraunhofer employed the risk matrix approach to visualize the outcomes of the risk analysis: likelihoods were calculated as described in section 5, using the 120-year average for daily mean gauging levels at station Kaub⁵. These likelihoods were categorized into the five different surcharge intervals provided by the Mannheim Large Powerplant, while the estimated impacts were categorized into six different impact classes.

Waterway transport surcharges grow exponentially with decreasing water levels. Certain water levels mark critical surcharge amounts: 220 cm (first significant rise), 150 cm, 100 cm, 50 cm, and 40 cm (highest cost, several times as high as normally). These water level (**wl**) values delimit surcharge relevant intervals **wli**₂, ..., **wli**₆ (in list order):

$$150 \text{ cm} < \text{wl} \leq 220 \text{ cm}$$

$$100 \text{ cm} < \text{wl} \leq 150 \text{ cm}$$

$$50 \text{ cm} < \text{wl} \leq 100 \text{ cm}$$

$$40 \text{ cm} < \text{wl} \leq 50 \text{ cm}$$

$$0 \text{ cm} < \text{wl} \leq 40 \text{ cm}$$

For determining likelihoods, we used water level data from gauging station Kaub⁶ for the 120-year spanning period 1900–2020. We first calculated the number of days per year in which the daily mean gauging level at Kaub falls within the surcharge relevant water level intervals. Based on these values, we then created a reference scenario by calculating the 120-year average number of days in each of the five intervals and then we calculated the fictive expected surcharge for an ‘average year’ (based on current surcharge rates) against which historical or fictive low water scenarios can be compared.

To determine the impact classes, Fraunhofer calculated the average transportation amount of coal—in tons—using the monthly transportation values for 2017 and 2018 provided by Mannheim Large Powerplant as reference. For these years, Fraunhofer estimated the additional transportation costs—the surcharge—using the number of days the gauging levels at station Kaub fell within a specific surcharge interval, i.e.,

$$I_j = \text{adtq} * \text{dwl}_j * s_j, \text{ where:}$$

I_j denotes the Impact contribution of surcharge interval j , $j \in \{2, \dots, 6\}$, i.e., the total annual transport surcharge in euros for water level interval **wli** _{j} , $j \in \{2, \dots, 6\}$,

adtq denotes the average daily coal transport quantity in tons,

dwl_j denotes the number of days per year in which the water level at gauging station Kaub was in water level interval **wli** _{j} , $j \in \{2, \dots, 6\}$, and

s_j denotes the surcharge costs per ton associated with water level interval **wli** _{j} , $j \in \{2, \dots, 6\}$.

The total impact $I_1 = \sum_{j=2}^6 I_j$ sums up the total annual transport surcharge.

⁵ The water level data have been kindly provided by the German Federal Institute of Hydrology.

⁶ The water level data have been kindly provided by the German Federal Institute of Hydrology.

Based on these calculated values, Fraunhofer decided on an initial impact classification C_k , $k \in \{1, \dots, 6\}$ using five empirically determined surcharge values, $Limit_1, \dots, Limit_5$. The impact I_j , $j \in \{1, \dots, 6\}$ belongs to impact class C_k where:

$$\begin{aligned} k = 1 & \quad \text{if } 0 \leq I_j \leq Limit_1 \\ k \in \{2, \dots, 5\} & \quad \text{if } Limit_{(k-1)} < I_j \leq Limit_k \\ k = 6 & \quad \text{if } Limit_5 < I_j \end{aligned}$$

These five thresholds are determined by stakeholders' risk management. For completing a standard risk matrix, the stakeholders also need to assign risk categories—typically three to five (the BBK uses four)—to each of the 30 possible combinations of impact and likelihood. The risk categories may indicate the type of action that is required to compensate the surcharge costs, like switching to cheaper transport modalities or saving money in other business areas.

Since fluvial water levels are highly volatile and low water days do not follow regular patterns, the authors proposed using the risk matrix representation for creating a decision support tool that helps comparing impacts (transport surcharges) and frequencies of low water days for a few scenarios.

Using the impact and likelihood classification, Fraunhofer designed a matrix with the likelihood classes on the x axis and the impact classes on the y axis. At each intersection of a likelihood class with an impact class, this matrix contains four cells, each representing additional transportation costs:

- 1) for the reference scenario year calculated based on the 120-year averages;
- 2) for the historical values of 2017;
- 3) for the historical values of 2018; and
- 4) for a user-defined fictive scenario year. In addition, the matrix contains one column that calculates (and categorizes as impact) the sum of all additional transportation costs under a given scenario. The scheme of the resulting matrix is shown in Figure 7.

The resulting tool allows entering all relevant data: distribution of low water days in the cost-relevant intervals, transport surcharge per such interval, and annual volume of fuel shipped via inland water transport. The scenario allows assessing the consequences of more frequent and severe low water situations and may aid decision-making. That is, the stakeholder may now answer questions like:

- “How did last year compare to an average year in terms of distribution of low water days and resulting surcharges?”
- “How would a year with even more extreme low water levels than 2018 compare to 2018 and to the average year?”
- “What total transport surcharges could we expect for three extreme years in a row?”

The four examples displayed in Figure 7 show that for all four scenarios the distributions and amounts of surcharge costs may be vastly different. Combined with improved water level forecast methods, the tool may support early preparedness for low water situations, optimizing transport modes and minimizing costs.

ing to the exposed elements they are related to. This is done by creating ‘exposure fields’ (i.e., transparent, labelled rectangles) into which impacts, sensitivities, and capacities are located, while hazards remain clustered in their own ‘hazard field’ at the very top of the Impact Chain. ‘Exposure fields’ can be nested, if exposed elements constitute a sub-group within another exposed element group (e.g., ‘at risk population groups’ and ‘vulnerable population groups’ are sub-groups of ‘general population’). ‘Exposure fields’ can also partially overlap, if impacts are affecting multiple exposed elements of different groups (e.g., ‘vulnerable population groups’ and ‘health infrastructure’).

Clustering impacts, sensitivities, and capacities within ‘exposure fields’ allows to show similarities and differences between exposed elements as well as identifying which exposed elements are affected “early” in the chain and which elements are only affected “late” in the chain. This approach also allows to identify adaptation measures for different groups of exposed elements that might reduce cascading effects (e.g., intervening early to reduce risk of serious health issues).

Impact chain modification B – Different stakeholders work with different exposed elements:

If the stakeholders involved in the risk analysis work with distinct, but potentially related sets of exposed elements (e.g., harbor infrastructure, container ships, and electricity production), we grouped impacts, sensitivities, capacities, and exposed elements in the Impact Chain into different ‘impact fields’, based on the fields of action of the German Adaptation Strategy (e.g., transport, industry, energy industry, water industry, ecology / hygiene, and tourism). Like the ‘exposure fields’, ‘impact fields’ are included in the Impact Chain as transparent, labelled rectangles into which all other Impact Chain elements, expect hazards, er located. ‘Impact fields’ can overlap, if they have impacts, sensitivities, capacities, or exposed elements in common, and they can also be nested, if it is necessary to distinguish between different sub-groups of impacts (e.g., changes to the ecosystem are defined as a sub-group of the ‘impact field’ ecology / hygiene). This approach adopts partly the systems concept introduced in the ISO standard 14090 [26].

Clustering impacts, exposed elements, sensitivities, and capacities within ‘impact fields’ allows to show interdependencies and potential cascading effects between businesses and ‘impact fields’. In addition, it allows to identify ‘joint’ adaptation measures and measures of one stakeholder that support another stakeholder, which can in turn allow to identify adaptation measures early in a Value Chain that help to reduce cascading effects for following businesses. This latter approach facilitates making adaptation efforts of different business partners transparent and allows fosters joint discussion, e.g., on distributing adaptation costs fairly across the Value Chain. For an example Impact Chain following this approach, see Appendix 4.

Impact chain modification C – Combining Impact Chains and Value Chains of individual businesses:

This modification assumes that an Impact Chain following modification A or B (or the ‘standard’ VSB visualisation) was already created (see also section 2). To combine such an Impact Chain with a Value Chain model, the Value Chain of the business under examination must be modelled. Here we employed a well-tested approach used by Fraunhofer in business consulting practices. First, the Value Chain of the business is divided into four separate sections: 1) input / supply (i.e., all process steps outside the business related to suppliers, input logistics, and inbound storage); 2) internal Value Chain (i.e., all process steps related to the internal value production); 3) internal support divisions (i.e., all supporting process steps that are relevant to enable the actual value production, but do not contribute directly to it); and 4) output / delivery (i.e., all process steps related to customers, output logistics, and assets).

After this separation, the different business units, their relevant process steps, and the relations between the different business steps are identified (e.g., via organigrams or business process documentation). Lastly, the Value Chain sections, business units, and process steps are visualized in diagrammatic form, similar to Impact Chains, with the input section either at the top or on the left, the internal Value Chain in the middle, the internal support division beside the internal Value Chain, and the output section at the bottom or on the right (see Figure 4).

Once this Value Chain model has been created, impacts, sensitivities, and capacities from the previously generated Impact Chain can be located within the Value Chain model, by placing them beside the process steps – which constitute the exposed elements of the combined impact / Value Chain. If Impact Chain elements cannot be related to individual process steps, it is also possible to locate them at the level of business units.

Locating Impact Chain elements within the Value Chain of a business allows to identify potential cascading effects that might otherwise be missed. In addition, this approach allows to locate potential adaptation measures within different business units or even process steps, subsequently allocating budget (or costs) to these units.

Additional information (“narratives” and other things)

To combine the information from the Impact Chains, Value Chains, and risk analysis with relevant additional information, Fraunhofer produced an eight-page dossier *“Evaluation of the Reports and Analyses on Economic Damage Caused by Summer Low Water in the Rhine”*. This dossier gathers information on the investigated risk, its impacts, adaptation measures (implemented, on-going, and planned), and policies (political and industrial). It has been produced by research in the scoping phase, by gathering stakeholder information during the co-production workshops, and by parallel research updates.

The dossier starts with describing the **economic impacts** of the 2018 record low water situation on the Rhine, stating economic losses of 2.4 billion euros in Germany and 295 million euros in the Netherlands and reporting more specific figures for some major industrial companies along the Rhine River. A 2018 study [3] pointed out that *“The importance of inland waterway transport compared to other modes of transport is particularly high for the goods divisions coal, crude petroleum and natural gas as well as coke and petroleum products, for which 28 and 21 percent respectively of the total transport volume was transported by inland waterway. These goods tend to be at the beginning of many production chains, so transport-related failures could lead to production disruptions in downstream production stages.”* That is, national and trans-national supply chains could be noticeably affected by long periods of low waters of the Rhine River.

Shifting the transport of goods to other modes of transport during periods of low water is an obvious solution, and one that is also practiced. However, there are several unfavorable boundary conditions related to **transport infrastructure**. On the one hand, the capacities of transport modes such as rail and truck are limited, but especially the aforementioned large volume goods would require huge road and rail transport capacities. A recent stress test study on traffic flows along the Middle Rhine states (translated from German with deepl.com): *“In practice, the extensive transport capacities of the waterway cannot be completely substituted by other modes of transport in the short term.”* A short-term increase in demand for transport capacity would also lead to higher transport

charges, which may lead to further unfavorable economic effects. In addition, there are also transportation problems with rail and truck modes. In recent years, there have been blockages of the right Rhine riverbank rail line for several weeks: in 2021, a seven-week blockage after rockfall near Kestert [40]; in 2017, a seven-week blockage after collapse of the tunnel structure near Rastatt [16]. In Germany, the planned expansion of the rail link between Genoa and Rotterdam to increase transport capacity is lagging far behind the schedule contractually agreed with neighboring countries. This line runs to a good part through the valley of the Rhine River. Road transport of goods suffers from the poor condition of bridge structures, especially along the Rhine, which lead to long detours, longer transport times and higher costs. Since July 2021, the situation of alternative modes of transport is exacerbated by the flood damages in NRW and Rhineland-Palatinate.

The narrative continues with reporting implemented and planned **adaptation measures**, like

- recooling systems for enabling the reuse of river water especially during periods in which discharge of cooling water is forbidden due to extreme heat;
- optimization of loading and unloading times for accelerated dispatch of the higher number of barges required in periods of low water levels;
- optimized or newly constructed facilities for uptake of river water from the Rhine;
- high-capacity storage systems for cooling water for air-conditioning workspace during periods of extreme heat;
- conversion of cargo ships for improved navigability during periods of low river water levels;
- improved medium- and long-term forecast of low water levels: a 10-day forecast is already operational, and a six-weeks forecast is being tested by users (typically logistics companies).

On the **policy** side, both national and international authorities and bodies are the actors. The German Federal Ministry for Digital and Transport (BMDV, formerly BMVI), for instance, has included a policy in its Federal Transport Infrastructure Plan for 2030 [9], namely “*off-loading optimization of the navigation channels on the Middle Rhine*”. This means leveling the riverbed of the Rhine River, especially at critical places like the Lorelei rock. Since the off-loading depths of barges must be adjusted to the shallowest points along the entire route, the leveling will improve the navigability of the Rhine, especially during low water periods. The implementation of this optimization measure is on-going.

Also, the BMVI has issued an eight-point “Action Plan Low Water Rhine” [7]. The short- to medium-term actions cover improvements in “provision of information”, “transport and logistics”, and “infrastructure”. Additionally, long-term actions comprise investigation of hydraulic engineering, including the leveling of the riverbed, and water management options to ensure reliably calculable transport conditions on the Rhine and social dialogue.

Such actions are complemented by the federal program “Blue Ribbon Germany” [8] for renaturation of flowing waters and water meadows of tributary waterways.

On an international level, the European Commission, the International Commission for the Protection of the Rhine (ICPR), and the Central Commission for Navigation on the Rhine (CCNR) contribute to policy making for the Rhine River.

Outcomes

Adjusted visualization of Impact Chains (‘exposure fields’ and ‘impact fields’); combined Value Chain / Impact Chain visualization; dossier with additional qualitative information

III. Key lessons learned per innovation area

Research innovation relating to Impact Chain method

- 1. Have you extended your methodology beyond what is described in the Vulnerability Sourcebook (this can be related to the 5 Innovations, but does not have to)?**

Yes.

- 2. How does your methodology extend the original Vulnerability Sourcebook [1] methodology?**

Extension a): In our approach, the co-production of Impact Chains is not started from scratch but uses relevant parts of the more general national (German) climate Impact Chains. The extracted parts comprise elements relating to the concrete climate risk, sectors, and fields of action under investigation in the case study. This approach has two effects: 1) co-production starts with concrete examples (and thus avoids “re-inventing the wheel”), and 2) the resulting qualitative ICs are consistent with the national ICs, which could be an advantage for subsequent adaptation measures and acquiring their funding.

Extension b): By connecting to individual stakeholders’ business continuity management in a subsequent analysis stage, the approach spans three levels of scale. The subsequent stage uses two approaches. First, it maps risk factors from the ICs onto elements—i.e., business units and processes—of a corporate Value Chain. Second, it analyses the risk contribution of an indicator that is associated with the risk factors by displaying it in a form like a risk matrix, which is a standard and familiar way of visualizing risk.

- 3. Which Sourcebook modules do your methodological extensions refer to (Which Sub-research question relates to which module can be looked up in the Case Study Protocol D2.1)?**

Extension a) refers to VSB modules M1 and M2 and contributes to RQ 1 and RQ 1.1.

Extension b) refers to VSB modules M2—M5, and M8 and contributes to RQ 1.1, RQ1.5 and RQ4.

- 4. How do you rate your methodological extensions in terms of the following validation criteria (short written reflections)? Please repeat the filling of the table for each Sourcebook module that you have methodologically extended.**

Extension a): Using parts of national Impact Chains as a starting point for regional and local Impact Chain creation

Criteria	Requirement	Answer
Relevance	Supports the identification of climate risks with the option to identify climate change adaptation measures - based on Impact Chains - with the aim to derive a quantitative and qualitative (or	Yes. Different from the original VSB module M1, the preparation started with employing the relevant parts of existing national German ICs as basis for the IC templates. In (online) co-production workshops, stakeholders

	both combined) climate risk assessment	enrich these elements by regional and stakeholder-specific risk factors. Exposure, impacts, capacities, and sensitivities are grouped by sectors and national fields of action. The resulting co-produced qualitative IC is consistent with the national ICs. Quantitative risk assessment can be performed in subsequent process steps. For Case Study 3, this has been done for a single industrial stakeholder.
Applicability	The method is generic in its application as well as not limited to exclusive/commercial toolsets	Yes. However, the pure online nature of stakeholder workshops requires using video conferencing tools, and the quantitative analysis requires spreadsheet calculation software.
Comprehensibility	The method is documented, and guidance is provided	The method is documented in detail. Guidance, incl. presentations, is provided.
Scientific Validity	The approach is scientifically valid (and re-producible) and has undergone a review (e.g., by another expert round, review etc.)	The approach is reproducible but has not yet been published in a peer-reviewed journal.
	The Impact Chains are based on a diverse set of stakeholder knowledge together with scientific findings	Yes, this is the case.
Effectiveness	The method can be implemented without primary data collection (i.e., it can be built on existing datasets)	Initial information on the regional situation is a must to win stakeholder trust. Specific datasets are not required before entering the quantitative assessment phase.
	The method allows the integration of data from heterogeneous data sources (quantitative, qualitative, expert, stakeholder...)	Yes.

	It can be implemented within a feasible timeframe and practicable team size	Yes.
	It involves stakeholders in all its main phases	Yes.
Transferability	The method can be transferred to other application/sector contexts	Yes.
	It can be transferred to other geographical settings	Yes.
Scalability	The method can be applied at different geographical scales (local, provincial, national, regional...)	Yes.
	It can be scaled across varying numbers of assessment units (e.g., 3-4 admin units vs. 15-20 admin units)	The method has been applied for two sets of admin units: five units for the first Impact Chain, eight units for the second Impact Chain.

Would you suggest this extension to be integrated into an updated version of the Vulnerability Sourcebook?

Yes. It could be an optional element in cases where Impact Chains for a higher governance level are available.

Extension b): Mapping risk factors from Impact Chains to corporate business Value Chains

Criteria	Requirement	Answer
Relevance	Supports the identification of climate risks with the option to identify climate change adaptation measures - based on Impact Chains - with the aim to derive a quantitative and qualitative (or both combined) climate risk assessment	By combining business Value Chains and ICs, national, local, and company-specific risk factors can be pinpointed in business processes and corporate departments and activities. The resulting VC enriched by risk factors is a qualitative result of the method. Further quantitative assessment using measurable indicators for

		critical risk factors has been performed in Case Study 3.
Applicability	The method is generic in its application as well as not limited to exclusive/commercial toolsets	Yes. For the qualitative part, standard online collaboration tools are required. For the quantitative part, spreadsheet calculation software is required.
Comprehensibility	The method is documented, and guidance is provided	The method is documented in detail. Guidance, incl. presentations, is provided.
Scientific Validity	The approach is scientifically valid (and re-producible) and has undergone a review (e.g., by another expert round, review etc.)	The approach is reproducible but has not yet been published in a peer-reviewed journal.
	The Impact Chains are based on a diverse set of stakeholder knowledge together with scientific findings	Yes. Using Value Chains for business analyses is an established concept from economics. The risk analysis cannot be performed without the stakeholder's knowledge of the company's business elements.
Effectiveness	The method can be implemented without primary data collection (i.e., it can be built on existing datasets)	The method requires the prior creation of at least one Impact Chain.
	The method allows the integration of data from heterogeneous data sources (quantitative, qualitative, expert, stakeholder...)	Yes.
	It can be implemented within a feasible timeframe and practicable team size	Yes.
	It involves stakeholders in all its main phases	Yes.
Transferability	The method can be transferred to other application/sector contexts	The method is designed specifically for corporations. It shall work for any economic sector.

	It can be transferred to other geographical settings	Yes.
Scalability	The method can be applied at different geographical scales (local, provincial, national, regional...)	The method should work for multi-corporate enterprises and their national and local substructures.
	It can be scaled across varying numbers of assessment units (e.g., 3-4 admin units vs. 15-20 admin units)	The method has been applied for two admin units of a corporation. Including experts from more units of the same corporation should work. Limitations are to be expected from availability of experts and group sizes up to which effective co-production can be maintained.

Would you suggest this extension to be integrated into an updated version of the Vulnerability Sourcebook?

Yes. It could be an optional element for risk assessment in the industry.

Research innovation relating to uncertainties

Uncertainties have not been addressed in Case Study 3.

Research innovation relating to co-production of knowledge

Regarding co-production of knowledge, there are two aspects worth mentioning:

1. The complete online implementation of the Impact Chain workshops
2. Conducting one multi-hazard & multi-stakeholder workshop

Ad 1) The complete online implementation of collaborating with stakeholder was due the Covid-19 pandemic that started at roughly the same time as Case Study 3 did. For co-producing Impact Chains and Value Chains, we employed online graphics tools in parallel to video conferencing software. The chosen graphics tool (*miro*) could be used in web browsers and allowed users to work simultaneously on different parts of a graphical figure. We had the impression that the ease of use and the direct availability constituted a lower barrier for making contributions than the physical pen/cardboard/pin wall combination. Thorough planning, a concise agenda, clear ideas about goals and desired results, and good facilitator skills seemed essential for conducting these events successfully.

Ad 2) The IC workshop for assessing the risk of more frequent periods of drought and summer low water of the Rhine River on infrastructure and logistics in the Mannheim region was a special challenge. There, we assessed several but related hazards simultaneously with a group of several different actors (several municipal departments, a state-owned organisation, and three industrial corporations). The

co-produced Impact Chain covered several fields of action of the German Adaptation Strategy. The new knowledge created included

- Pinpointing risk factors from German national ICs to regional stakeholders and exposures
- Pinpointing local and regional risk factors to fields of action of the German Adaptation Strategy
- Examples of adaptation measures that have already been implemented or that are planned
- Additional local and regional impacts and causal relationships
- Insights into best practices of other stakeholders

The good level of trust that was achieved during the preparatory meetings facilitated these results.

From the obtained information, we concluded that indicators and adaptation measures are business- and location-specific when it comes to industrial facilities. While adaptation measures like green roofs and enlarged sewer system capacities are quite general, the lowering of river water uptake inlets or the assessment of water transport surcharges for freight apply only to certain industries located at inland waterways.

Research innovation relating to societal change and socio-economic consequences

In [32], p. 9, the authors discuss scenario-based approaches for assessing impacts of climate change on traffic flows in the Middle Rhine region. Besides the well-known RCP climate scenarios, the authors propose complementary *stress test scenarios*. They state (translated from German with deepl.com):

“An alternative approach to assessing the impact of extreme events is the definition of so-called stress test scenarios. Here—first of all independently of the climate development projected by the models—a scenario is defined that represents a particularly large, theoretically possible but so far unobserved possible, but not yet observed, stress for the system under consideration. Through the hypothetical assumption of an extreme weather-related, long-lasting or significantly reduced capacity of selected stretches of the German transport network due to extreme weather German transport network, the effects of such potential events on supra-regional traffic flows and the on supraregional traffic flows and the corresponding possibilities for shifting traffic can be evaluated. Based on the system understanding thus generated, conclusions can be drawn about the resilience and redundancy of the transport system in the study area, and different reaction and adaptation options can be discussed.”

Similarly, the proposed tool for assessing transport surcharges for low water levels of the Rhine River allows formulating different low water scenarios that have not yet been observed or recorded but may occur in future extreme weather or climate conditions. While this may be a valuable decision-support tool on a corporate level, we would also point to another statement in the same publication, namely:

“As the low water in 2018 has shown, the economic effects of such an extremely long-lasting low water situation are many times higher than the additional transport costs considered here, which refer purely to the additional costs of transporting the goods.” [32]

A hazard like an extended low water period would affect several hundreds of kilometers of the Rhine River and all settlements and industries along the river. This would add up to a severe economic damage via cascading effects. Comprehensive assessments of the implications of such large-scale scenarios requires collaboration of experts in several different domains. Typically, this cannot be done on the level of smaller corporations or municipalities. This task would rather require federal or state agencies, large business consultancy firms, think tanks, or insurance companies.

Research innovation relating to transborder climate change risks

Mapping of climate Impact Chains to Value Chains, logistics as connecting element

The approach used in Case Study 3 connects three levels of scale. As a starting point at the highest level, we extracted relevant parts from the general German national climate Impact Chains. The extracted parts comprise elements relating to the concrete climate hazard, sectors, and fields of action under investigation in the case study. Next, a regional climate Impact Chain was created (multi-hazard, multi-stakeholder). Finally, pinpointing risk factors from the regional IC to a corporate Value Chain connecting to individual stakeholders' business continuity management. For clarification, the reader should note that these activities are sub-processes of the qualitative risk assessment part of the Vulnerability Sourcebook method.

Figure 10 in the Appendix shows the suggested use of Impact Chains at these different levels of scale:

- Step 0: extract relevant parts from national ICs
- Step 1: create a regional climate Impact Chain building upon parts of the national ICs
- Step 2: map risk factors from the regional climate Impact Chain to the corporate Value Chain and categorize them: process risk and management risk are internal factors, supply and demand side risk are external factors
- Step 3 (not applied): identify potential cascading of climate risk along a supply chain: leverage point for managing risk jointly with suppliers and customer. The connecting elements at both 'ends' of a corporate Value Chain are the input logistics (supply side risk / suppliers) and output logistics (demand side risk / customers)

This would allow to communicate external risk factors and related adaptation measures with customers and suppliers, that is, supporting for climate risk management along supply chains. If done properly, this joint risk management could make supply chains more resilient against cascading effects. The logistics as connecting element has, in our globalized world, a trans-border dimension. The supplier and customer relations in supply chains are often trans-sectoral.

Adaptation of the visualization of the Impact Chain

The *Risk Supplement to the Vulnerability Sourcebook* [20] proposes a visualization of the Impact Chain that clusters its main elements exposure, hazards, intermediate impacts, and vulnerability (comprising sensitivities and capacities) in large boxes, one per each type of element. We deviated from this approach by clustering intermediate impacts, exposed elements, sensitivities, and capacities within 'impact fields.' Many — but not all — sensitivities, capacities and intermediate impacts were directly related to specific exposed elements. Thus, we clustered these related elements together when possible, highlighting their connectedness. This way, we found it easier to show interdependencies and potential cascading effects between businesses and 'impact fields.' In addition, this clustering facilitates identifying 'joint' adaptation measures and measures of one stakeholder that support another stakeholder, which may in turn help identifying adaptation measures early in a Value Chain that are suited to reduce cascading effects for following businesses. This latter approach allows making adaptation efforts of different business partners transparent and fostering a joint discussion, e.g., on distributing adaptation costs fairly across the Value Chain. The integration of the designations of national fields of action identifies connections to the German Adaptation Strategy. This is important because there are documents

detailing funding instruments and opportunities for adaptation measures for each of the twelve German National Fields of Action [13], [33].

Appendix 1: References

- [1] Fritzsche, K., Schneiderbauer, S., Bubeck, P., Kienberger, S., Buth, M., Zebisch, M., Kahlenborn, W. (2014). *The Vulnerability Sourcebook. Concept and Guidelines for Standardized Vulnerability Assessments*. Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) GmbH, Germany.
- [2] Ademmer, M., Jannsen, N., Möhle, S. (2020): *Extreme weather events and economic activity: The case of low water levels on the Rhine River*, Kiel Working Papers 2155, <https://www.ifw-kiel.de/de/experten/ifw/saskia-moesle/extreme-weather-events-and-economic-activity-the-case-of-low-water-levels-on-the-rhine-river-14220/>
- [3] Ademmer, M., Boysen-Hogrefe, J., Fiedler, S., Groll, D., Jannsen, N., Kooths, S., Möhle, S., Potjagailo, G. (2018): *Aufschwung stößt an Grenzen – Belegung nur temporär*, Kieler Konjunkturberichte Nr. 50 (2018|Q4), <https://www.ifw-kiel.de/de/publikationen/kieler-konjunkturberichte/2018/aufschwung-stoesst-an-grenzen-belegung-nur-temporaer-11863/>
- [4] BBK (2011): *German Federal Office of Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance: Method of Risk Analysis for Civil Protection*. Wissenschaftsforum, Volume 8, Bonn. ISBN: 978-3-939347-41-5.
- [5] Binnenschifffahrt Online (2020): *Wenig Wasser – hoher Schaden*, 1.5.2020, <https://binnenschifffahrt-online.de/2020/05/schifffahrt/14614/>
- [6] Binnenschifffahrt Online (2020): *Langfristige Vorhersage von Niedrigwasserständen möglich*, 6.8.2020, <https://binnenschifffahrt-online.de/2020/08/haefen-wasserstrassen/15890/langfristige-vorhersage-von-niedrigwasserstaenden-nun-moeglich/>
- [7] Bundesministerium für Digitales und Verkehr (BMDV) (2019): *Aktionsplan „Niedrigwasser Rhein“ für zuverlässigen Transport*. Berlin, Juli 2019. <https://www.bmvi.de/SharedDocs/DE/Artikel/WS/gemeinsame-erklaerung-acht-punkte-plan-niedrigwasser-rhein.html>
- [8] Bundesverkehrsministerium (BMVI) und Bundesumweltministerium (BMU) (2018): *Bundesprogramm Blaues Band Deutschland*. Bonn, Juli 2018. www.blaues-band.de
- [9] BMVI (2016): *The 2030 Federal Transport Infrastructure Plan*. Berlin, Germany, August 2016. <https://www.bmvi.de/SharedDocs/EN/Articles/G/federal-transport-infrastructure-plan-2030.html>
- [10] BMVI (2015): *KLIWAS – Auswirkungen des Klimawandels auf Wasserstraßen und Schifffahrt in Deutschland*. Abschlussbericht des BMVI – Fachliche Schlussfolgerungen aus den Ergebnissen des Forschungsprogramms KLIWAS. BMVI, Berlin, Germany.
- [11] BMZ (2013): *Perspektiven der Urbanisierung – Städte nachhaltig gestalten*. Information brochure of German Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development, Germany.
- [12] Bundesregierung (2008): *Deutsche Anpassungsstrategie an den Klimawandel* vom Bundeskabinett am 17. Dezember 2008 beschlossen. Berlin, Deutschland, 2008. <https://www.bmuv.de/download/deutsche-anpassungsstrategie-an-den-klimawandel>
- [13] Bundesregierung (2011): *Aktionsplan Anpassung der Deutschen Anpassungsstrategie an den Klimawandel* vom Bundeskabinett am 31. August 2011 beschlossen. Berlin, Deutschland, 2011.
- [14] Bundesverband der Deutschen Binnenschifffahrt e.V. (2019): *Daten und Fakten 2018/2019*, https://www.binnenschiff.de/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/191125-Daten-Fakten_2018-19_final.pdf.

- [15] Bundesverband der Deutschen Binnenschifffahrt e.V. (2020): *Daten und Fakten 2019/2020*, https://www.binnenschiff.de/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/Daten-Fakten_2019-20_final.pdf.
- [16] Deutsche Welle (2017): *Die Rheintalbahn bleibt lange dicht*, DW, 22.8.2017, <https://www.dw.com/de/die-rheintalbahn-bleibt-lange-dicht/a-40189895>
- [17] European Commission COM(2021) 82 final, “Forging a climate-resilient Europe - the new EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change”, Brussels, 24.2.2021
- [18] European Commission COM(2019) 640 final “The European Green Deal”, Brussels, 11.12.2019
- [19] European Commission COM(2020) 829 final “Proposal for a DIRECTIVE OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on the resilience of critical entities”, Brussels, 16.12.2020
- [20] GIZ (2017): Risk Supplement to the Vulnerability Sourcebook. *Guidance on How to Apply the Vulnerability Sourcebook’s Approach with the New IPCC AR5 Concept of Climate Risk*. Bonn, Germany, 2017.
- [21] Hänsel, S., Nilson, E., Patzwahl, R., Forbriger, M., Klose, M., Krieger, B. (2020): *Einflüsse naturgefahrenbedingter Streckensperrungen auf überregionale Verkehrsströme – Verkehrsträgerübergreifende Stresstestszenarien für die Region ‚Mittelrhein‘*. Schlussbericht des Schwerpunktthemas Fokusgebiete Binnen (SP-109) im Themenfeld 1 des BMVI-Expertennetzwerks (Simulation einer extrem langen Niedrigwasserperiode)
- [22] IfW-Box 2018.17 *Zum Einfluss des Niedrigwassers auf die Konjunktur*, IfW Kiel, 2018, https://www.ifw-kiel.de/fileadmin/Dateiverwaltung/IfW-Publications/-ifw/IfW_Box/2018/box_2018-17_niedrigwasser.pdf
- [23] IPCC (2014a): *Climate Change 2014: Mitigation of Climate Change*. Contribution of Working Group III to the Fifth Assessment Report to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- [24] IPCC (2014b): *Climate Change 2014: Synthesis Report*. Contribution of Working Groups I, II and III to the Fifth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change [Core Writing Team, R.K. Pachauri and L.A. Meyer (eds.)]. IPCC, Geneva, Switzerland, 151 pp.
- [25] IKS (2018): *Bestandsaufnahme zu den Niedrigwasserverhältnissen am Rhein*. Stand: 04.05.2018, Bericht Nr. 248, IKS, Koblenz (Tiefgehende Analyse der Niedrigwassersituation am Rhein als Vorbereitung für Anpassungsmaßnahmen)
- [26] ISO 14090:2019: Adaptation to climate change — Principles, requirements and guidelines.
- [27] Kersten, W., Singer, C. (2011): *Aufbau von Flexibilitätspotenzialen zur Beherrschung von Supply Chain-Risiken*. Industrie Management, Vol. 27, No. 3, 61-64.
- [28] Kind, C., Savelsberg, J., Lühr, O., Kramer, J.-P., Lambert, J. (2014): *Klimacheck – Leitfaden zum Management von Klimarisiken im industriellen Mittelstand*. Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Energie (BMWi, Hrsg.), Berlin, Deutschland, Oktober 2014.
- [29] LUBW Landesanstalt für Umwelt Baden-Württemberg (2020): *Monitoringbericht 2020 zur Anpassungsstrategie an den Klimawandel in Baden-Württemberg*. Stuttgart, Dezember 2020.
- [30] LUBW Landesanstalt für Umwelt Baden-Württemberg (2013): *Zukünftige Klimaentwicklung in Baden-Württemberg: Perspektiven aus regionalen Klimamodellen*. Stuttgart, Februar 2013.
- [31] Lückerath, D., Streberová, E., Bogen, M., Rome, E., Ullrich, O., Pauditšová, E. (2020): *Climate Change Impact and Vulnerability Analysis in the City of Bratislava: Application and Lessons Learned*, Proceedings of CRITIS 2019, the 14th International Conference on Critical Information Infrastructures Security, Linköping, Sweden, 24.-26.9.2019, Springer LNCS 11777, p. 83–94.

- [32] Nilson, E. et al. (2021): *Beiträge zu einer verkehrsträgerübergreifenden Klimawirkungsanalyse: Wasserstraßenspezifische Wirkungszusammenhänge*. Schlussbericht des Schwerpunktes Schiffbarkeit und Wasserbeschaffenheit (SP-106) im Themenfeld 1 des BMVI-Expertennetzwerks (Beitrag zu den Impact Chains der Dt. Anpassungsstrategie)
- [33] NRW (2015): *Klimaschutzplan Nordrhein-Westfalen – Klimaschutz und Klimafolgenanpassung*. Ministerium für Klimaschutz, Umwelt, Landwirtschaft, Natur- und Verbraucherschutz des Landes Nordrhein-Westfalen (ed.), Düsseldorf, Germany, 2015.
- [34] Porter, M.E. (1985): *Competitive Advantage: Creating and Sustaining Superior Performance*. New York.: Simon and Schuster, ISBN 9781416595847.
- [35] Porter, M.E. (1991): Towards a dynamic theory of strategy. *Strategic Management Journal*, 12, p. 95–117.
- [36] Rome, E., Ullrich, O., Lückerath, D., Worst, R., Xie, J., Bogen, M. (2019): *IVAVIA: Impact and Vulnerability Analysis of Vital Infrastructures and Built-Up Areas*, Proceedings of CRITIS 2018, the 13th International Conference on Critical Information Infrastructures Security, Kaunas, Lithuania, 24.-26.9.2018, Springer LNCS 11260, p. 84-97.
- [37] Rome, E., Bogen, M., Lückerath, D., Ullrich, O., Worst, R., Streberová, E., . . . Carter, J. (2019). *Risk-based analysis of the vulnerability of urban infrastructure to the consequences of climate change*. In D. Gritzalis, M. Theocharidou, & G. Stergiopoulos (Eds.), *Advanced Sciences and Technologies for Security Applications. Critical Infrastructure Security and Resilience: Theories, Methods, Tools and Technologies* (pp. 55-75). Retrieved from <https://www.springer.com/us/book/9783030000233>
- [38] Schneiderbauer, S., Zebisch, M., Kass, S., Pedoth, L. (2013): *Assessment of vulnerability to natural hazards and climate change in mountain environments – examples from the Alps*. In: J Birkmann (ed): *Measuring Vulnerability*, 2nd edition, ISBN-13: 978-81-7993-122-6, ISBN: 81-7993-122-6, United University Press, pp 349.
- [39] Streng, M., van Saase, N., Kuipers, B. (2020): *Economische impact laagwater – Een analyse van de effecten van laagwater op de binnenvaartsector en de Nederlandse en Duitse economie*, Erasmus Centre for Urban, Port and Transport Economics, April 2020.
- [40] Süddeutsche Zeitung (2021): *Bahn will Rheinstrecke am 2. Mai eingleisig öffnen*. SZ, München, 16.04.2021. <https://www.sueddeutsche.de/wirtschaft/bahn-kestert-bahn-will-rheinstrecke-am-2-mai-eingleisig-oeffnen-dpa.urn-newsml-dpa-com-20090101-210416-99-227714>
- [41] Ullrich, O., Bogen, M., Lückerath, D., Rome, E. (2019): *Co-operating with Municipal Partners on Indicator Identification and Data Acquisition*. Simulation Notes Europe SNE 29(4), 2019, 159-168. DOI: 10.11128/sne.29.on.10491
- [42] Umweltbundesamt (Hrsg.) (2021): *„Klimawirkungs- und Risikoanalyse 2021 für Deutschland. Teilbericht 4: Risiken und Anpassung im Cluster Infrastruktur“* von M. Voß, W. Kahlenborn, L. Porst, L. Dorsch, E. Nilson, E. Rudolph, A.-F. Lohrengel. Dessau-Roßlau, Juni 2021.
- [43] Umweltbundesamt (Hrsg.) (2019): CLIMATE CHANGE 20/2019 *„Folgen des globalen Klimawandels für Deutschland. Erster Teilbericht: Die Wirkungsketten in der Übersicht“* von M. Peter, M. Guyer, Dr. J. Füssler (INFRAS, Zürich). Dessau-Roßlau, September 2019.
- [44] Umweltbundesamt (Hrsg.) (2017): *„Leitfaden für Klimawirkungs- und Vulnerabilitätsanalysen – Empfehlungen der Interministeriellen Arbeitsgruppe Anpassung an den Klimawandel der Bundes-*

regierung“ von M. Buth, W. Kahlenborn (adelphi); S. Greiving, M. Fleischhauer (plan + risk consult); M. Zebisch, S. Schneiderbauer (Europäische Akademie Bozen); I. Schauser (UBA). Dessau-Roßlau, Februar 2017.

- [45] Umweltbundesamt (Hrsg., 2016): „Klimawirkungsketten Umweltbundesamt 2016“. Dessau-Roßlau, Dezember 2016.
https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/380/dokumente/klimawirkungsketten_umweltbundesamt_2016.pdf
- [46] Umweltbundesamt (Hrsg., 2021): Niedrigwasser, Dürre und Grundwasserneubildung – Bestandsaufnahme zur gegenwärtigen Situation in Deutschland, den Klimaprojektionen und den existierenden Maßnahmen und Strategien. Abschlussbericht.
https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/1410/publikationen/2022-01-17_texte_174-2021_niedrigwasser_duerre_und_grundwasserneubildung.pdf
- [47] ZKR (CCNR), *Jahresbericht 2019*, Strasbourg, Frankreich, https://inland-navigation-market.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/11/ccnr_2019_Q2_de-min2.pdf

Appendix 2: Figures and Diagrams

National German Impact Chain, excerpt for low water IC

Ausschnitt aus der Klimawirkungskette des UBA (2016)

Zu analysierendes Risiko:

Auswirkungen häufigerer Perioden von Trockenheit und Sommerniedrigwasser des Rheins auf Infrastruktur und Logistik in der Region Mannheim

Handlungsfelder:

- Wasserhaushalt, Wasserwirtschaft
- Energiewirtschaft
- Verkehr, Verkehrsinfrastruktur
- Industrie, Gewerbe
- Tourismuswirtschaft

Sensitivitäten & Kapazitäten

Figure 8: Excerpt of the German national Impact Chains, starting point for developing the low water IC in Case Study 3. After:

https://www.umweltbundesamt.de/sites/default/files/medien/380/dokumente/klimawirkungsketten_umweltbundesamt_2016.pdf

Complete, final, validated Impact Chain for low water risk

Figure 9: Final, complete, validated Impact Chain for the risk of impacts of more frequent periods of drought and summer low water of the Rhine River on infrastructure and logistics in the Mannheim region (in German).

- Lower orange box: Risk statement
- Upper blue box: Hazards / Threats
- Vertical blue-green box: Adaptation measures
- Middle light grey boxes: Fields of action from national ICs
- Small purple rectangles: External factors
- Right box column: Definitions of used terms
- Upper line of colored boxes: Explanation of elements of the Impact Chain (legend)
- Within the fields of action, there are exposures, intermediate impacts, sensitivities, capacities, and arrows indicating causal relationships. Dark grey circles are comments.

From national Impact Chains to impacts cascading along supply chains

0) National Impact Chain (excerpt)

1) Case Impact Chain

2) Risk-enhanced Value Chain of a company

3) Risk management along the Supply Chain

Figure 10: Suggested use of Impact Chains at different levels of scale. Step 0: extract relevant parts from national ICs; step 1: create a regional case IC; step 2: map risk factors to the corporate Value Chain; step 3 (not applied): potential cascading of risk along a supply chain: leverage point for managing risk jointly with suppliers and customers

Appendix 3: List of Acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
ARA	Amsterdam, Rotterdam, Antwerp (seaports)
AR5	(IPCC) Assessment Report 5
BBK	Bundesamt für Bevölkerungsschutz und Katastrophenhilfe (German Federal Office for Civil Protection and Disaster Assistance)
BMDV	Bundesministerium für Digitales und Verkehr (Federal Ministry for Digital and Transport)
BMZ	Bundesministerium für wirtschaftliche Zusammenarbeit und Entwicklung (Federal Ministry for Economic Cooperation and Development)
BMWi	Bundesministerium für Wirtschaft und Klimaschutz (Federal Ministry for Economy)
CCNR	Central Commission for the Navigation of the Rhine (German: ZKR)
CPK	Co-production of knowledge (IC innovation area)
EU	European Union
EUROSTAT	Statistical office of the European Union
GKM	Großkraftwerk Mannheim (Mannheim Large Powerplant)
IC	Impact Chain
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
ICM&U	Impact Chain Model & Uncertainty (IC innovation area)
IPCC	Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change
RQ	Research Question
SC	Supply Chain
SES	Socio-economic Scenarios (IC innovation area)
TBCCI	Transborder climate change impacts (IC innovation area)
UBA	Umweltbundesamt (Federal Environmental Agency)
VC	Value Chain
VS	Vulnerability Sourcebook
WP5	Work package 5
ZKR	Zentralkommission für die Rheinschifffahrt (English: CCNR)